

Depressive Disorder and Neuro-Behçet's disease: About a Clinical Case

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ABSTRACT Behçet's disease is a chronic, relapsing and multisystemic vasculitis. To emphasize the importance of the psychiatric manifestations of Behçet's disease, we will discuss the case of a 45-year-old patient with no psychiatric history. It has been followed for 2 years for Behçet's disease, since taking corticosteroids and colchicine. For the past three months, he has presented psychiatric demonstrations evoking a depressive episode, which was complicated by an attempted suicide by self-immolation, hence his hospitalization in psychiatry.

Psychiatric involvement is controversial: there are specific manifestations of Behçet's disease or comorbidity. It is sometimes worrying because of the risk of depression related to corticosteroids. The management of comorbidity Behçet's disease and depressive disorder requires a multidisciplinary approach.

KEYWORDS Neuro-Behçet's disease, depression, corticosteroids, multidisciplinary

Introduction

Behçet's disease is a multi-systemic chronic inflammatory disease that affects all types of blood vessels. Hulusi Behçet, a Turkish dermatologist, described in 1937 a triad associating oral aphthosis, genital aphthosis and uveitis. It is generally characterized by recurrent cutaneous and mucosal lesions and also involves major organs, including the central nervous, gastrointestinal, musculoskeletal and ophthalmic systems. Its chronic and recurrent nature leads to an increase in morbidity and mortality. It mainly affects the young adult, with an average age between 22 and 31 years. The sex ratio in Behçet's disease is difficult to determine and remains controversial. It differs in the series according to the specialities. Population survey data show a fairly balanced male-female distribution.

The aetiology of Behçet's disease has not been fully illuminated. Indeed, several factors have been incriminated, mainly genetic predisposition, autoimmunity and viral and bacterial

infections. Also, physical and psychological stress has been suggested in the development of autoimmune diseases. In addition, several studies have shown that there is a stressor in most patients with Behçet's disease before the onset or relapse of the disease. Psychiatric manifestations during Behçet's disease are diverse. They can range from sleep disturbance to psychotic disorders, to anxiety-depressive disorders with a significant risk of suicide.

The assessment of depression in subjects with Behçet's disease, like other chronic inflammatory diseases, is a challenge, especially since the somatic symptoms of depression clearly overlap with the symptoms and complications of the disease.

The interest of our work is based on a higher prevalence of depression in patients with chronic illness. Through a clinical case, we will focus on a depressive episode characterized by severe intensity complicating Behçet's disease while emphasizing the importance of multidisciplinary care.

Patient and observation

He is Mr B.A. 45 years old, married and father of 2 children, a native and living in Khemisset, civil servant, mutualist. He was admitted to the psychiatric emergency department of the Arrazi University Psychiatric Hospital in Salé to take charge of attempted suicide by self-immolation. Indeed, the patient is followed for 2 years for Behçet's disease. He is on treatment with oral corticosteroids: Prednisone 5mg / day and Colchicine 1mg

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/ day. In his antecedents, one finds a keto-ketosis coma from where his hospitalization and his put on oral antidiabetic one year ago. Three months before his hospitalization in psychiatry, he presented neurological manifestations of Behçet's disease made of hemiplegia rocking and diplopia where his hospitalization in the internal medicine department with a good improvement under treatment made of high-dose corticosteroid therapy (3 intravenous boluses of 1 g of methylprednisolone followed by 1 mg / kg / day of oral prednisone) and cyclophosphamide. Gradually after leaving the hospital, he became irritable, asthenic, sad, slow and anhedonia with a sense of hopelessness and incurability that was complicated by an attempt to commit suicide by self-immolation on the day of his admission. In his office alone, in a depressive environment narrowly saved by his colleagues from where admission to the psychiatric emergency department of the Arrazi University Psychiatric Hospital in Salé. The psychiatric interview on admission found a patient anxious, slightly unstable on the motor, adapted corporeal-clothing but with a strong smell of gasoline used for his suicide attempt, mimic little mobile, easy and fruitful contact. His basic psychic activities are preserved. His speech is slow. He cries at times during the interview. His thought is the seat of guilt, incurability and low self-esteem. It does not report perceptual disturbances. His mood is sad, and his affect is concordant. He is insomniac, and his appetite is diminished. The examination did not reveal an underlying personality disorder. Concerning his suicide attempt, he does not regret it; he did it in a frame of despair and incurability. He reports that he cannot cure his illness, that it is disabling and that he sees his future blocked. The diagnosis is that of a depressive episode characterized according to the diagnostic criteria of the DSM-5. (Box 1) The evolution in the service was marked by the stabilization on the motor level, the acceptance of the care, the recovery of the sleep and the improvement of the mood with the disappearance of the suicidal ideation. He came out stabilized 1 month later, under Escitalopram 20mg / day and Quétiapine Lp 150mg / day with cognitive-behavioural psychotherapy. Currently, the patient regularly goes to his post-cure appointments.

Discussion

Behçet's disease is a chronic inflammatory disease of the vasculitis type, characterized clinically by oral or more often bipolar aphtosis (oral-genital), associated with cutaneous, ocular, articular, neurological, cardiovascular and intestinal systemic manifestations. It is common in the Middle East, Japan, and the countries around the Mediterranean. Its prevalence varies between 3,3 and 21 per 100,000 inhabitants . This affection of the young subject (20-30 years old), of male sex most often, is rarely discovered after 50 years. The average age of diagnosis is between 32 and 36 years, except in the Middle East series, where the age is lower (22-29 years).

The diagnosis is based on criteria established by the international study group on Behçet's disease in 1990. These criteria were reviewed in 2013 (14) to establish a score whose sensitivity for diagnosis is better (95% vs 85%), and the specificity remains very good (91% vs 96%) (Table 1). Neuro-psycho-Behçet is a neurobehavioral syndrome that can be characterized by memory, personality, disinhibition and mood disorders. A study by Fraison et al. including 98 patients with Behçet's disease followed between 2000 and 2012, found that 27.5% of patients had a psychiatric disorder, 89% had depression, 11% had bipolar disorder, and 7.4% had bipolar disorder. A psychosis. Indeed,

Behçet's disease is systematically associated with depression, with an incidence of 86% from the first appearance of symptoms of the disease. Also, anxiety and depression are common in patients with Behçet's disease (8 to 50%), and 86% of patients have concomitant psychosomatic symptoms. Psychological disorders may play a role in the aetiology of the disease, but may also occur as a result of Behçet's disease. In our patient, the causal link between Behçet's disease and depression has not been well established. Is it a neuro-Behçet, or comorbidity, or should we suspect an iatrogenic effect of corticosteroids?

Although not yet clarified, disease progression, functional deterioration, central nervous system involvement and corticosteroid use have been suggested as factors related to depressive symptomatology in patients with of Behçet's disease. Several studies have also reported the existence of a stressor in most of these patients before the onset or relapse of the disease. Also, the activity of the disease can be implicated as one of the factors related to depression in these patients. In neuro-Behçet, psychiatric manifestations, such as anxiety and depression, are rarely caused by direct organic damage to the central nervous system. Nevertheless, they are rather secondary to the disease, the fatigue, the functional deterioration and the socio-professional handicap generated . In his study, Birkan Ilhan et al. to determine the relationship between fatigue in patients with Behçet's disease and depression and anxiety, found that fatigue was more common in these patients than in healthy controls. In addition to increased fatigue, these patients had a lower quality of life, increased anxiety, and depression compared to healthy controls. Fatigue was significantly higher in patients with active Behçet disease and also correlated with disease activity. These findings underscore the importance of managing fatigue to prevent depression in patients with Behçet's disease. According to the study done by Ender Taner et al., the duration of the disease was a significant risk factor for the development of depression in patients with Behçet's disease. These results indicate the need to recognize and quickly manage psychiatric symptoms in these patients. Regarding suicidal ideation, in a study by Saygin C et al. concluded that patients with Behçet's disease who have significant organ damage have more and more suicidal thoughts during the active stages of their disease. This suggests the importance of adapting treatment according to the type and severity of the disease. A study by Faruk Uguz et al. suggests that depression is a significant factor affecting the quality of life of patients with Behçet's disease.

Some authors have reported that successful treatment of depression improves the quality of life of patients with a medical condition. Similarly, the quality of life of patients with Behçet's disease can be improved during the treatment of comorbid depression.

Conclusion

Behçet disease is a systemic vasculitis that can affect multiple organs. Psychiatric involvement is a factor of the severity of the disease. Depression is a common disorder in Behçet's disease; it may be comorbid or secondary to a Neuro-Behçet or corticosteroid therapy.

Screening for psychiatric disorders is necessary as part of a multidisciplinary approach to the disease to provide comprehensive care and prevent the passage from a suicidal act.

Competing Interests

No conflict of Interest.

Box 1: Diagnostic criteria for a depressive episode characterized by DSM-5 as proposed by the American Psychiatric Association.

- A. 1. Depressed mood most of the day, almost every day, indicated by your own subjective report or by the report of others. This mood might be characterized by sadness, emptiness, or hopelessness.*
- 2. Markedly diminished interest or pleasure in all or almost all activities most of the day nearly every day.*
- 3. Significant weight loss when not dieting or weight gain.*
- 4. Inability to sleep or oversleeping nearly every day.*
- 5. Psychomotor agitation or retardation nearly every day.*
- 6. Fatigue or loss of energy nearly every day.*
- 7. Feelings of worthlessness or excessive or inappropriate guilt (which may be delusional) nearly every day.*
- 8. Diminished ability to think or concentrate, or indecisiveness, nearly every day.*
- 9. Recurrent thoughts of death (not just fear of dying), recurrent suicidal ideation without a specific plan, or a suicide attempt or a specific plan for committing suicide.*
- B. Symptoms cause clinically significant distress or impairment in social, occupational, or other important areas of functioning*
- C. The episode is not due to the effects of a substance or to a medical condition*
- D. The occurrence is not better explained by schizoaffective disorder, schizophrenia, schizophreniform disorder, delusional disorder, or other specified and unspecified schizophrenia spectrum and other psychotic disorders*
- E. There has never been a manic episode or a hypomanic episode*

Table 1 New international criteria for Behçet’s disease. A score ≥ 4 is in favor of the diagnosis

Sign/symptom	Points
Ocular lesions	2
Genital aphthosis	2
Oral aphthosis	2
Skin lesions	2
Neurological manifestations	2
Vascular manifestations	2
Positive pathergy test*	2

*Pathergy test is optional and the primary scoring system does not include pathergy testing. However, where pathergy testing is conducted one extra point may be assigned for a positive result (1).

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